

Bio-ethanol adsorption on bone-char

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Abstract

Separation of bioethanol via adsorption on appropriately selected adsorbents is an economical and environmentally friendly method for its recovery. During the last years a number of studies employed adsorption of ethanol on natural adsorbents and activated carbons.

In the present work the adsorption of ethanol on commercial bone char (Brazil, 40-50-number of sieve) was tested. For that reason kinetic and isotherm experiments were conducted. Two series of experiments served for the study of the kinetics. Samples of 10 mL containing 0.05 g of char were employed. The initial concentration of ethanol was 5 g L⁻¹ for the first and 10 g L⁻¹ of ethanol for the second series. Three isotherms were performed at each concentration at 20, 30, 40 °C at pH 7 and at 30 °C at pH 6. The samples were placed in a constant temperature bath and were continuously agitated at 120 rpm for up to 48 hours depending on the measurement.

The bone char was capable to adsorb ethanol. The adsorption capacity was a function of temperature and substrate concentration. At 30°C, a larger quantity of ethanol was adsorbed as compared to respective measurements at 40°C. In all cases, the adsorption rate was very fast during the first 10 h of treatment approaching equilibrium with minimal ethanol being adsorbed for the following 20-38 h of treatment.

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